

Gender differences in cardiorespiratory fitness and body fat among Nigerian teenagers

Hanif S.¹ ABCDEF, Musa DI.² ABCDEF, Lamina S.³ ABCDEF, Nuhu JM.¹ ABCDEF, Ahmad RY.¹ ABCDEF

¹Physiotherapy Department, Faculty of Allied Health Sciences, Bayero University, Kano.

²Human Performance Laboratory, Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

³Medical Rehabilitation Department, Faculty of Health Sciences and Technology, University of Nigeria, Enugu Campus.

Received March 24. 2017, Accepted May 26.2017

Abstract

Background: Cardiorespiratory fitness (CRF) and body fat are both predictors of health risks reported among Nigerians.

Objective: To determine gender differences in obesity and physical fitness among North-west Nigerian teenagers.

Method: This cross-sectional correlational study included 394 teenagers. Subjects underwent anthropometric and physiological evaluations. Prevalence of obesity and low work capacity (LWC) (males ≤ 42 ; females ≤ 35 ml.kg⁻¹.min⁻¹) were assessed. The Peak Vo₂ was assessed using the 20meters multi-stage shuttle run test (PACER).

Result: Of the total 394 teenagers, there were 195 (49.5%) males and 199 (50.5%) females. Obesity was not prevalent in the study population. Low work capacity was significantly prevalent and there was a significant difference in body fat and Peak Vo₂ between males and females, with females having greater body fat and lower Peak Vo₂ values. Body fat was negatively correlated to Peak Vo₂. Descriptive statistics was used to summarize the data. Independent t-test was computed to compare physical/anthropometric characteristics across gender and fitness groups. Chi-square was computed to determine difference in prevalence of obesity and LWC between male and female teenagers using Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS), Version 20.0 at P<0.05.

Conclusion/Recommendation: Gender has influence on the prevalence of LWC among 13-19 yr old children in North-west Nigeria. Early detection and treatment of LWC and more studies of this nature should be conducted in other regions in both affluent and poor communities in this country.

Keywords: cardiorespiratory; fitness; teenagers; gender

Introduction

Obesity has been recently identified as a major independent risk factor for coronary heart disease (CHD) by the American Heart Association [AHA][1]. Gender might significantly affect the degree of tracking of obesity in children and youth[2]. Sadly, obesity is not just a problem for adults. Overweight children tend to become overweight adults[3]. According to Falkner and Michel[4], obesity in children and teenagers seem to be on the rise over the past 3 decades, and this increasing prevalence, especially in big cities, has become a significant public health problem[5].

The well-known Bogalusa heart study found that approximately 25% of children between the ages of 6-19yr were overweight, which may place an alarming number of children and adolescents at an increased risk for CHD[6]. Physical inactivity has been established as a major risk factor for the development of CHD[7]. Prevalence of inactivity varies by gender, age and geographic

region but is common to all demographic groups[8]. A review of 43 epidemiological studies found that physical inactivity was associated with double the risk of developing CHD. Also, studies showed that a young person who is physically active also continues to be active as an adult[9]. Studies of preschool, preadolescent, adolescent, and adult subjects showed males to be somewhat more physically active than females[10].

Previous reports have described findings of obesity and physical inactivity in pre-school children[9-11], school-aged children (5-14 yr, 7-12 yr, 9-11 yr, 8-15 yr, 10-15 yr and 13-15 yr)[12-22], and middle-aged population[23,24]. However, research is yet to be conducted on teenage (13-19 yr old) subjects. Studies in both female and male teenagers have been limited in North-west Nigeria and not sufficiently extensive to produce conclusive results. This study was designed to determine the prevalence of obesity and physical inactivity among male and female teenagers in North-west Nigeria.

METHODS

Cross-sectional survey research design was used in this study which included 394 males and females of ages 13-19 years in selected Unity Secondary Schools in North-west Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling technique was used to obtain the sample.

The purpose and procedure of this study was explained to the participants after due permission had been obtained from the Principals of the schools. Written informed consent was obtained from the Principals of the schools on behalf of the parents and the subjects, as recommended by the human subject protocol, before participation in the study.

Subjects' height was measured to the nearest 0.5 centimeter (cm) while standing erect bare-footed, against a calibrated wall with their feet together on a level floor. A horizontal broad blade plastic ruler was rested on their heads and the height was read off from the wall. Subjects were in minimum clothing and without shoes. Body mass was measured to the nearest 0.5kg with a portable weighing scale. Respondents' BMI was derived as a ratio of his/her weight (in Kilogram) to height (in meters) squared (kg/m^2)[15]. Skinfold measurement was used to predict percent body fat, fat mass (FM), and lean body mass (LBM). Subjects' skinfold thickness was measured on the right side of the body to the nearest millimeter (mm) using Harpenden skinfold caliper (Creative Health Products, MI, U.S.A.) as recommended by Heyward[25]. Skinfold measurement was taken at the triceps and the calf. The regression equations of Lohman[2] were used to estimate relative body fat from the sums of triceps and calf skinfolds:

Males: % fat = $0.735 \sum \text{SF} + 1.0$

Females: % fat = $0.610 \sum \text{SF} + 5.0$; where, $\sum \text{SF}$ = sum of

skinfolds.

Fat mass was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{FM} = \frac{\text{BM} \times \% \text{fat}}{100}$$

Lean body mass (LBM) was calculated as suggested by McArdle, Katch and Katch[26]: $\text{LBM} = \text{BM} - \text{FM}$

The subjects' cardiorespiratory fitness was assessed using the 20m multi-stage shuttle run test (20-MST) also called Progressive Aerobic Cardiovascular Endurance Run (PACER). The PACER was performed in accordance with the one minute protocol by Leger and Lambert[27] using a PACER tape. Subjects' scores were converted to Peak Vo_2 scores using the regression equation presented by Plowman and Smith[28]:

$$\text{Peak Vo}_2 = 31.025 + 3.238 (\text{final speed in km/hr}) - 3.248 (\text{age in yr}) + 0.1536 (\text{final speed} \times \text{age}).$$

In order to assess the relationship between cardiorespiratory fitness and obesity, the total sample was divided into two groups on the basis of each subject's peak Vo_2 value, using cut-off points of $\leq 42 \text{ ml.kg}^{-1}.\text{min}^{-1}$ for males and $\leq 35 \text{ ml.kg}^{-1}.\text{min}^{-1}$ for females which represented the subjects' median value. The two groups were as follows: Group 1: $\leq 42 \text{ ml.kg}^{-1}.\text{min}^{-1}$ for males; $\leq 35 \text{ ml.kg}^{-1}.\text{min}^{-1}$ for females (Low fit); Group 2: $> 42 \text{ ml.kg}^{-1}.\text{min}^{-1}$ for males; $> 35 \text{ ml.kg}^{-1}.\text{min}^{-1}$ for females (High fit).

Data analysis: Statistical analysis included descriptive statistics (Means \pm SD) and inferential statistics. The student t-test was used to compare physical and physiological characteristics across the gender and fitness groups in teenagers in North-west Nigeria. Chi-square analysis was also used to determine the significance of

Table 1: Analysis of the subjects' physical and physiological characteristics by gender (N=394)

Variable	Female (N=199)		Male (N=195)		t-value
	x	SD	x	SD	
Age (yr)	16.1	2.2	16.1	2.0	0.060
Height (cm)	159.3	6.6	166.0	9.0	8.364**
BM (kg)	50.9	8.1	53.7	10.2	3.106**
FM (kg)	10.0	4.0	6.2	3.4	10.074**
LBM (kg)	40.8	5.6	47.5	9.1	8.803**
BMI (kg.m^{-2})	20.0	2.6	19.7	2.7	2.350*
Body fat (%)	19.3	5.4	11.5	5.2	14.757**
Peak Vo_2 ($\text{ml.kg}^{-1}.\text{min}^{-1}$)	35.2	5.0	44.6	6.0	16.998**

*P<0.05, **P<0.01

Table 2: Percentage of body fat and Vo₂max by gender among teenagers

Riskfactor	Criteria	Female	Male	Total studypopulation
		(N=199)	(N=195)	(N=394)
Body fat (%)	≥ 25	4(1.0%)	-	4 (1.0%)
	≥ 32	-	6(1.5%)	6(1.5%)
Vo ₂ max (ml/kg/min)	≤ 35	99 (25.1%)	-	99 (25.1%)
	≤ 42	-	61 (15.5%)	61(15.5%)

differences in obesity and low work capacity prevalence between males and females. All the statistical analysis was performed on a microcomputer using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) (Windows Version 20.0, Chicago, IL, U.S.A.). For all the analysis, an alpha level of $P \leq 0.05$ was used to indicate statistical significance.

RESULTS

Of the total sample of 394 teenagers, there were 199 females and 195 males. The means and standard deviations of subjects' physical and physiological characteristics by gender are presented in Table 1.

There were significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in their physical and physiological characteristics with respect to height, BM, FM, LBM, BMI, body fat and Peak Vo₂ between females and males. The means revealed in all cases, the females had a significantly higher FM, BMI and body fat in contrast to the males; while the males had a significantly greater height, BM, LBM and Peak Vo₂ compared to their female counterparts.

Chi-square was computed to find out if there is significant difference in prevalence of obesity and LWC between male and female subjects. Table 3 shows the summary of chi-square on subjects' obesity and LWC by gender.

The result of the chi-square indicated no significant ($P > 0.05$) difference in prevalence of obesity between

males and females; and a significant ($P < 0.01$) difference in prevalence of LWC between males and females.

The results of this study also revealed that there was a significant relationship between physical fitness and body fat. The relative high negative correlation between relative body fat and Peak Vo₂ ($r = -0.470$) suggests that subjects with low peak Vo₂ values are not fit and probably have a sedentary life-style.

Table 4 details the descriptive analysis ($\bar{x} \pm SD$) of the physical characteristics and CHD risk factors of subjects by fitness group.

With regards to the general characteristics of the groups, significant differences were found for age ($P < 0.001$), height ($P < 0.001$), FM ($P < 0.001$), LBM ($P < 0.05$), BMI ($P < 0.001$), body fat ($P < 0.001$) and Peak Vo₂ ($P < 0.001$) with the low fit group demonstrating higher age, FM, BMI and body fat; whereas the high fit group demonstrated greater height, LBM, and Peak Vo₂. No significant ($P > 0.05$) differences were found for BM.

Table 5 provides an analysis of the number and percentage of subjects with obesity & LWC in each fitness group.

More subjects in the low fitness group 9 (4.5%) had obesity compared to only 1 (0.5%) from the high fitness group. Similarly, a greater proportion of subjects with low work capacity were from the low fitness group as compared to those in the high fitness group.

Table 3: Chi-square summary on subjects' obesity and LWC by gender

Variables	GENDER	
	Female (N=199)	Male (N=195)
Obesity ($X^2 = 0.453$)		
Normal	FO	195
	FE	193.9
High	FO	4
	FE	5.1
LWC ($X^2 = 13.926$)*		
Normal	FO	100
	FE	118.2
Low	FO	99
	FE	80.8

$X^2_{(9)} = 16.92$ (* $P < 0.05$); 21.67 (** $P < 0.01$)

Table 4: Physical and physiological characteristics of subjects by fitness group

Variable	Low fit group	High fit group	t-value
	193 (49%) ($\bar{x} \pm SD$)	201 (51%) ($\bar{x} \pm SD$)	
Age (yr)	16.8 \pm 1.9	15.5 \pm 2.0	6.779**
Height (cm)	161.4 \pm 7.6	163.7 \pm 9.2	2.728**
BM (kg)	53.0 \pm 8.4	51.6 \pm 10.1	1.392
FM (kg)	9.8 \pm 4.5	6.5 \pm 3.2	8.389**
LBM (kg)	43.1 \pm 7.1	45.1 \pm 9.1	2.387*
BMI (kg.m ⁻²)	20.3 \pm 2.7	19.1 \pm 2.5	4.463**
Body fat (%)	18.3 \pm 6.6	12.6 \pm 5.1	9.561**
Peak Vo ₂ (ml.kg ⁻¹ .min ⁻¹)	33.8 \pm 3.6	45.7 \pm 4.5	28.734**

t₍₃₉₂₎ = 1.960 (*P<0.05); 2.576 (**P<0.01)

Table 5:CHD risk factors in high fitness and low fitness groups

Riskfactor	Criteria	Low fit group (N=193)		High fit group (N=201)		Total (N=394)	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Body fat (%)	≥ 25	6	3.0	0	0.0	6	2.5
	* ≥ 32	3	1.5	1	0.5	4	1.0
Peak Vo ₂ max	≤ 42	36	18.7	25	12.4	61	15.5

* Lower values for females

DISCUSSION

The means and standard deviation of the physical characteristics of the subjects are similar to those reported in the literature[12,13,17]. The average BF values reported in this study were found to be lower than the "at-risk" value for obesity in 13-19yr old females and males according to the Cooper Institute for Aerobics [CIAR][29] and the National High BP Education Programme[30]. The Peak Vo₂ for this sample was within the range according to sex and age, i.e. the mean Peak Vo₂ values were above the "at-risk" levels for both the females and males according to the CIAR[29], indicating the sample had a better than average cardiovascular endurance capacity.

Prevalence of obesity in this study indicates that it is not identifiable in the teenagers of this study. Of the total study population, 2.5% were considered obese. Gilliam et al.[13], Khattab et al.[31] and Underhay et al.[22] reported obesity to be the most prevalent in their studies. The proportion of the subjects with obesity reported by Gilliam et al.[13] for the total population in Michigan was much more than that reported in this study; though, the cut-off points used in this study were different only for the female subjects but were the same for the males. Wilmore and McNamara[12] also reported a higher proportion (13%) of obesity in their 8-12 yrs old male subjects. Their finding is in contrast to the findings of the

present study probably because they used an arbitrary adult standard of 20% body fat. Similarly, Wilmore et al.[12] observed a higher proportion of males (13-15yrs old) in Tucson who were considered obese (body fat >25%). Lauer et al.[32] found a higher proportion of their 14-18 yrs old population with obesity. These differences may be accounted for due to differences in the ethnic group of the subjects probably due to their level of physical fitness. Musa[21] reported that obesity was a prevalent risk factor in his study of 9-11yrs old females. This finding is in contrast to that reported in the present study. The prevalence of obesity among the female subjects of this study is less and in contrast to the female subjects of Musa[21] who had a prevalence rate of 20.5% (body fat>20) and 4.5% (body fat>25). It is not surprising that there is a higher rate of obesity despite the age bracket of his sample. Musa's[21]sample was made up of children from high and middle socio-economic class, while that of this study included mostly low socio-economic class children.

There was no significant difference in prevalence of obesity between the male and female subjects. This finding is not consistent with that reported by Khattab et al.[31], Lawoyin et al.[31]and Underhay et al.[22] who used subjects >20yrs, 15-30yrs and 10-15yrs respectively and reported that females were more obese than their male counterparts. Gilliam et al.[22]reported prevalence

of obesity (>25%) for the 7-12 yrs old females and males of their study in Michigan. These investigators observed that 8.5% of the males and 2.1% of females in their study were obese. This result is similar to that reported in this present study with regards to gender, i.e. more males (1.5%) were obese compared to females (1.0%) but it was at odds to this study because their proportion of males and females with obesity were significantly different compared to that of this study. The cut-off points used in this study were similar in the case of males but that used for the females was higher which may have accounted for a lower proportion of females with obesity. The regional difference may also have accounted for the difference in prevalence rates.

The present study revealed considerable prevalence of LWC in the subjects. This finding is consistent with that of Gilliam et al.[13], Musa[21] and Underhay et al.[22]with regards to LWC being prevalent in their sample population. More than 1/3rd of the subjects of this population had LWC. This prevalence is much higher than that of Cappuccio³⁴ who revealed that 1/4th of his population was inactive. This result shows that the subjects of this study are less fit than those reported by Cappuccio[34].

There was a significant difference in prevalence of LWC between males and females. The females had a higher prevalence (25.1%) of LWC compared to the males (15.5%). This result is consistent with the findings of Armstrong et al.[17]and Hansen et al.[35] who similarly reported a gender difference in physical fitness. The reason for this could be due to lack of exposure of the females in this part of Nigeria probably due to religious and cultural factor.

The prevalence rate of LWC in females was found to be higher in this study compared to that reported by Gilliam et al.[13] who observed that 11 % of their female subjects had LWC. This value is much less than that estimated in this study in the female subjects (25.1%). This difference may be accounted due to variation in socioeconomic class, as the subjects used by Gilliam et al. were of higher socio-economic class, hence have more opportunity to keep themselves fit and are more privileged to better environment for exercises to keep fit. Wilmore et al.[14] reported a higher proportion of 13-15yrs old males in Tucson which is in contrast to the 15.5% observed in this study. This difference could be due to differences in the regions of the subjects.

When the risk factor prevalence was analyzed in relation to the subject's level of fitness (Table 5), higher proportion (4.5%) of subjects with obesity were found in the low fit group; whereas, a lower proportion (0.5%) of subjects with obesity was found in the high fit group. This result is in line with that reported by Wilmore et al.[14]

and Kwee and Wilmore[19]. The result of this study also shows that no male was found to be obese in the high fit group and only 0.5% of the females were found to be obese in the high fit group. More females than males with obesity were found in the high fit group.

Prevalence of LWC was much higher in the low fit group as compared to the high fit group. This finding is similar to that reported by Musa, Ibrahim and Toriola[8] and Wilmore et al.[12]. No female had LWC in the high fit group; this result is similar to that reported by Musa[21]; whereas 12.4% of the males of this study were found to have low work capacity in the high fit group. In the low fit group, more females than males had LWC; this may probably be due to the fact that females have a more sedentary life style in this part of Nigeria.

The results of this study also revealed that there was a significant relationship between physical fitness and body fat. The relative high negative correlation between relative body fat and Peak Vo₂ ($r = -0.470$) suggests that subjects with low peak Vo₂ values are not fit and probably have a sedentary life-style. This result is in line with that reported by Wilmore et al.[14]. The results of this study also indicate that decreasing levels of physical fitness were associated with increasing levels of body fat.

Conclusion/ Recommendation

Findings from this study indicated that obesity is not prevalent while substantiating the prevalence of LWC in teenagers of North-west Nigeria. The data have indicated a negative relationship between physical fitness and body fat; furthermore, it was concluded that prevalence of LWC was higher in the low fit group. Potential interventions in teenage years merit further investigation. No age is too young to start monitoring fitness level and counseling teenagers about their life style may be warranted. As part of the preventive measures, secondary school children (in North-west Nigeria should be provided with the opportunity to engage in increased regular and appropriate exercise programs in order to keep their fitness within desirable levels.

References:

1. American Heart Association. Heart attack, stroke and risk factors: NFPT Personal Trainer Magazine, 1997; 3: 5-7.
2. Lohman T.G. Advances in body composition assessment. Campaign: Human Kinetic Publishers. Current Issues in Exercise Science, 1992; 3: 91-97.
3. Taylor H., Leitman R. The epidemic: Americans continue to get fatter, with 80% over recommended weight and 33% who are now 20% or more overweight. HealthCare Interactive, 2002; 2 (6): 15-21.
4. Falkner B., Michel S. Obesity and other risk factors in children. EthnDis, 1999; 9: 284-289.

5. Seidell J.C., Flegal K.M. Assessing obesity: Classification and epidemiology. *British Medical Bulletin*, 1997; 53 (2): 238-252.
6. Freedman D., Dietz W.H. Srinivasan S.R., Berenson G.S. The relation of overweight to cardiovascular risk factors among children and adolescents: The Bogalusa study. *Pediatrics*, 1999; 103 (6): 1175-1181.
7. American Heart Association. Youth is no guaranty against heart disease. Available on-line: <http://www.hearthealthykids.com>. 2002.
8. Musa D.I., Ibrahim D.M., Toriola A.L. Cardiorespiratory fitness and risk factors of coronary heart disease in pre-adolescent Nigerian girls. *Journal of Human Movement Studies*, 2002; 42: 455-465.
9. Montoye H.J. Physical activity, physical fitness, and heart disease risk factors in children. In G.A. Stall & H.M. Eckert (Eds.), *The Academy of Physical Education Papers*. Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics. 1998.
10. Sallis J.F., Simons-Morton B.G., Stone E.J., Corbin C.B., Epstein L.H., Faucette N., Ionnotti R.J., Killen J.D., Klesges R.C., Petray C.K., Rowland T.W., Taylor W.C. Determinants of physical activity and interventions in youth. *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 1999; 24 (6): 248-257.
11. Berenson G.S., Srinivasan S.R., Bao W., Newman W.P., Tracy R.E., Wattigney W.A. Association between multiple cardiovascular risk factors and atherosclerosis in children and young adults. The Bogalusa heart study. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 1998; 338 (23): 1650-1656.
12. Wilmore J.H., McNamara J.J. Prevalence of coronary heart disease risk factors in boys, 8 to 12 years of age. *The Journal of Pediatrics*, 1974; 84 (4): 527-533.
13. Gilliam T.B., Katch V.L., Thorland W., Weltman A. Prevalence of coronary heart disease risk factors in active children, 7 to 12 years of age. *Medicine and Science in Sports*, 1997; 9 (1): 21-25.
14. Wilmore J.H., Constable S.H., Stanforth P.R., Tsao W.Y., Rotkis T.C., Paicius R.M., Mattern C.M., Ewy G.A. Prevalence of coronary heart disease risk factors in 13- to 15- year- old boys. *Journal of Cardiac Rehabilitation*, 1992; 2 (3): 223-233.
15. Fraser G.E., Phillips R.L., Harris R. Physical fitness and blood pressure in school children. *Circulation*, 1983; 2: 405-411.
16. Gilliam T.B. Coronary heart disease risk in children and their physical activity patterns. In R.A. Beileau (Ed.), *Advances in Pediatric Sports Sciences: Vol. 1. Biological Issues*. Champaign, IL: Human Kinetic Publishers; 1994.
17. Armstrong N., Balding J., Gentle P., Kirby B. Estimation of coronary risk factors in British school children: A preliminary report. *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 1990; 24 (1): 61-66.
18. Després J., Bouchard C., Malina R.M. Physical activity and coronary heart disease risk factors during childhood and adolescence. In K.B. Pandolf & J.O. Holloszy; Series Eds., *Exercise and Sport Sciences Reviews: Vol. 18*. American College of Sports Medicine Series. Baltimore: Williams and Wilkins; 1990: pp 243-261.
19. Kwee A., Wilmore J.H. Cardiorespiratory and risk factors for coronary artery disease in 8- to 15-year-old boys. *Pediatric Exercise Science*, 1990; 2: 372-383.
20. Sady S.P., Berg K., Beal D., Smith J.L., Savage M.P., Thompson W.H., Nutter J. Aerobic fitness and serum high-density lipoprotein cholesterol in young children. *Human Biology*, 1999; 56 (4): 771-778.
21. Musa D.I. Prevalence of coronary heart disease risk factors in preadolescent female school children in Kano City: A preliminary investigation. *Journal of Nigerian Association of Women in Sports*, 2002; 2 (1): 9-
22. Underhay C., DeRidder J.H., VanRooyen J.M., Krugger H.S. The influence of ethnicity on the prevalence of obesity and high blood pressure among 10-15 year old children. Pre-Games Scientific Congress Theme. *Moving Sports in Africa into New Frontiers. Programs and Abstracts*, 2003; pp 68.
23. National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute Growth & Health Study Research Group. Obesity and cardiovascular disease risk factors in Black and White Girls: The NHLBI Growth and Health Study. *American Journal of Public Health*, 1992; 82 (12): 1613-1620.
24. Caspersen C.J., Heath G.W. The risk factor concept of coronary heart disease. Resource manual for guidelines for exercise testing and prescription. American College of Sports Medicine. 2nd Ed. USA: Waverly Company, 1999.
25. Heyward V.H. Advanced fitness assessment and exercise prescription. 4th Ed. Human Kinetics: Champaign IL, 2012.
26. McArdle W.D., Katch F.I., Katch V.L. Exercise physiology: Energy, nutrition and human performance. 3rd Ed. Philadelphia: Lea &Febiger, 1991.
27. Leger L., Lambert J.A. Maximal 20 meters shuttle run test to predict VO₂ max. *European Journal of Applied Physiology*, 1992; 49: 1-12.
28. Plowman W., Smith A. Exercise physiology for health and performance. 2nd Ed. San Francisco: Benjamin Cummings, 1997.
29. Cooper Institute for Aerobics Research (1999). Fitness administration manual. 2nd Ed. Dallas, Texas: Human Kinetics.
30. National High Blood Pressure Education Program The fifth report of the joint committee on detection, evaluation, and treatment of high blood pressure. Washington, D.C., 1993.
31. Khattab M.S., Abolfotouh M.A., Alakija W., Al-Humaidi M.A., Al-Wahat S. Risk factors of coronary heart disease: Attitude and behavior in family practice in Saudi Arabia. *Saudi Medical Journal*, 1999; 5 (1): 35-45.
32. Lauer R.M., Connor W.E., Leaverton P.E., Reiter M.A., Clarke W.R. Coronary risk factors in school children. The Muscatine study. *J Pediatr*, 1995; 86: 697-706.
33. Lawoyin T.O., Asum M.C., Kaufman J., Rotimi P., Owoaje E., Johnson L., Cooper R. Prevalence of cardiovascular risk factors in an African, urban inner city community. *Nigerian News Now*, 1998; 5: 21.
34. Cappuccio F.P. Cardiovascular risk factors in different ethnic groups in a geographically defined area of South London. (Online). Available Internet: <http://www.cardio.riskfact/ethnicgp/4-3/io/html>; 2002.
35. Hansen H.S., Hyldebrandt N., Froberg K., Nielson J.R. Blood pressure and physical fitness in school children. *Scandinavian Journal of Laboratory Investigation*, 1989; 49: 42-46.

Corresponding Author:

Rufai Yusuf Ahmad
 Department of Physiotherapy
 Bayero University, Kano.
 Kano State, Nigeria.
 Email: ryahmad.pth@buk.edu.ng
 Phone: +2348036370098

Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.